

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D1.8 Data Management Plan and list of agreements with data providers, M6

29/02/2024

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D1.8 – Data Management Plan and list of agreements with data providers, M6

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0.3	27/02/2024	Nathalie Tonné (SSBE)	Review by Nathalie Tonné
1.0	29/02/2024	Lynn Delgat (VLIZ)	First version of DMP

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
DMP	Data management plan
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
DwC	DarwinCore
DwC-A	DarwinCore Archive
EDITO-infra	EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean
eDNA	environmental DNA
EMODnet	European Marine Observation & Data Network
EU DTO	European Union Digital Twin of the Ocean
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
MIxS	Minimum Information about any (X) Sequence
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System

Keywords

Data management, data flow, data standards, FAIR data, biodiversity data

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ocean and its biodiversity are essential to life on this planet. Comprehensive data on biodiversity, and related human and environmental pressures are crucial to understand its current state and how this may change. The EU will build on “a digital knowledge system” to include a Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) allowing simulation of ‘what if’ scenarios, advancing ocean knowledge, informing evidence-based policy and offering a range of societal applications. The DTO-BioFlow project will develop and integrate the biological component of the EU DTO, including new digital tools and services, by combining sustained data flows, models and new algorithms.

The biological component of the EU DTO requires sustained flows of biodiversity data, which are being collected by a myriad of actors, using a wide variety of methods. The use of novel cost-effective monitoring technologies (imaging, acoustics, DNA based, satellite) makes it possible to perform biodiversity observations at scales and frequencies that were previously unreachable. However, much biodiversity data remains unavailable, inaccessible, of unknown quality, not standardized and/or not interoperable with biodiversity data collected through other methods. Therefore, to have a truly functional biodiversity component of the EU DTO, a step change in the way biodiversity relevant data is collected, standardised, analysed, and made available is required. The DTO-BioFlow project will enable the sustainable integration of data flows from various sources to EMODnet and into the EDITO infrastructure serving the EU DTO, focusing on (semi-)automated procedures to ensure the data flows are sustained after the project ends. This will result in a huge leap forward in terms of allowing faster ingestion of new monitoring data by setting protocols and workflows towards a full-fledged DTO by 2030.

This document describes the data management approaches and responsibilities within DTO-BioFlow, towards ensuring that the data become FAIR and Openly Accessible, by publishing data in trusted repositories using internationally recognized standardized formats documented with rich metadata. It also gives an overview of the types, formats and sources of data that will be used in the project, gives a synopsis of the envisaged general data flow, and discusses the resource allocation and the ethical aspects related to the data collection in the project. Furthermore, this document contains a template for the agreements with data owners who receive an FSTP grant through the calls organised in Task 2.5. This document is the first version of the data management plan (DMP), which is a living document and will be updated throughout the project at regular intervals.

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1. Introduction

1.1. About this document

This document describes the data management approaches and responsibilities within DTO-BioFlow, towards ensuring that the data become FAIR and Openly Accessible. This is the first version of the data management plan (DMP), which is a living document and will be updated throughout the project at regular intervals. The consortium will be invited to give their input on the Data Management Plan and an updated version of the DMP will be published in month 18 of the project (D1.9). A final version of the DMP will be delivered before the end of the project (D1.10). A Data (Protection) Officer will oversee the data management plan and data protection strategy (T1.4), and their implementation in the project. This Data (Protection) Officer will be appointed by the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ). Furthermore, this document contains a template for the agreements with data owners who receive an FSTP grant through the calls organised in T2.5, in order to integrate missing biodiversity data sources into the DTO architecture and environment.

1.2. Project partners

1. VLIZ - VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE
2. EMBRC-ERIC - EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM
3. Lifewatch ERIC - E-SCIENCE EUROPEAN INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH
4. SSBE - SEASCAPE BELGIUM
5. UGOT - GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET
6. DTU - DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET
7. ICES - INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL FOR THE EXPLORATION OF THE SEA
8. COISPA - FONDAZIONE COISPA ETS
9. CSC - CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIKAN KESKUS OY
10. MOi - MERCATOR OCEAN
11. UNESCO - UNITED NATIONS EDUCATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND CULTURAL ORGANIZATION
12. SU - SORBONNE UNIVERSITE
13. TNO - NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO
14. SINTEF - SINTEF AS
15. SINTEF OCEAN - SINTEF OCEAN AS
16. TRUST-IT - TRUST-IT SRL
- 16.1. COMMpla - COMMPLA SRL
17. NATURALIS - STICHTING NATURALIS BIODIVERSITY CENTER
18. CIIMAR - CENTRO INTERDISCIPLINAR DE INVESTIGACAO MARINHA E AMBIENTAL
19. MARIS - MARIENE INFORMATIE SERVICE MARIS BV
20. CSIC - AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS
21. GEOMAR - HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL (GEOMA)
22. IT4I@VSB - VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
23. AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITET
24. HEREON - HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM HEREON GMBH
25. EMBL - EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY
26. CNRS - CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS
- 26.1. ULCO - UNIVERSITE DU LITTORAL
27. HCMR - HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH
28. EV INBO - EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR NATUUR- EN BOSONDERZOEK
29. MBA - MARINE BIOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION OF THE UNITED KINGDOM
30. USTAN - THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ST ANDREWS

1.3. Project summary

The ocean and its biodiversity are essential to life on this planet. Comprehensive data on biodiversity, and related human and environmental pressures are crucial to understand its current state and how this may change. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore our oceans and waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Identified as one of the Mission "enablers", **the EU will build on "a digital knowledge system" to include a Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO)** allowing simulation of 'what if' scenarios, advancing ocean knowledge, informing evidence-based policy, and offering a range of societal applications.

To effectively replicate the ocean's ecology, **the EU DTO requires sustained flows of data on biodiversity** and associated pressures. Despite myriad actors collecting biodiversity data, and the development of novel cost-effective monitoring technologies, much of these data are inaccessible or unusable for a variety of reasons, hampering the development of the DTO biological component and limiting its efficacy.

DTO-BioFlow will activate access to ("sleeping") marine biodiversity data and enable the sustainable integration of existing and new Artificial Intelligence processed and automated data flows from various sources to EMODnet and into the EDITO infrastructure serving the EU DTO. **Combining sustained data flows, models and new algorithms, DTO-BioFlow will develop and integrate the biological component of the EU DTO**, including new digital tools and services.

Policy-relevant use cases will demonstrate the benefit for marine ecosystems of continuous data streams flowing through EMODnet and usable by the EU DTO infrastructure and ultimate end-users. Mobilising the marine biodiversity community towards increasing the availability of biodiversity monitoring data into 2030, DTO-BioFlow and its outputs will support the Mission's actions to protect and restore biodiversity.

2. Data summary

2.1. Purpose of data collection/generation

The overall aim of DTO-BioFlow is to build the biological component of the Digital Twin of the Ocean, which will require large amounts of biodiversity data. The project aims to establish and/or promote sustained data flows from various data sources (e.g. existing monitoring programs, data owners of 'sleeping data') to EMODnet and into the EDITO infrastructure serving the EU DTO, and making these data available in an integrated and interoperable way, thus allowing simulation of 'what if' scenarios, advancing ocean knowledge, informing evidence-based policy and offering a range of societal applications.

2.2. Types and formats of data

2.2.1. Data types

All data handled within the project will be biological data, however there are several different subcategories that will be dealt with specifically in the project:

1. Genetic data
2. Plankton imaging data
3. Biologging data
4. Passive acoustic data
5. Other sources

Most of these data types comprise both raw data (e.g. images, sequences, audio files) and derived data (e.g. taxonomically annotated tabular data). The DTO-BioFlow project will mainly focus on establishing data flows for derived data, since these allow integration across data types.

Genetic data

Genetic data are data based on the DNA of organisms, which can be collected through various molecular methods. The two main methods that will be the focus in the DTO-BioFlow project are metabarcoding and metagenomics, specifically sequencing environmental DNA (eDNA).

Plankton imaging data

Quantitative imaging instruments are able to take large quantities of images in a consistent manner. From these images, qualitative and quantitative information can be derived, such as taxonomical information, morphological measurements, abundance, etc.

Biologging data

Biologging data are data of animal positions/presences obtained by animal-borne electronic devices. It can be divided into three types: GPS tracking, archival tracking, and acoustic telemetry.

Passive acoustic data

Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) is the monitoring of sounds made by marine animals. It is an important method for estimating the distribution, density, and abundance of species that vocalize. It is particularly useful for animals that frequently produce species-specific vocalizations, such as for example Harbor porpoises (*Phocoena phocoena*).

Other sources

This section addresses data sources not covered in the previous sections. This includes species occurrence data from global platforms not yet included in EMODnet Biology, gridded species distributions from various projects, report data from EU Directives reporting, industry data, citizen science data, and literature data. The data sources in this section are widely varied, and a lot of the specific details to bring these data into the EU DTO still require further discussion and planning with the other project WPs, for example to identify other relevant biodiversity data sources for the Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) in WP4.

2.2.2. File formats

The table below gives an overview of recommended file formats for the different data types described above. For completeness, a distinction is made between raw and derived data. However, DTO-BioFlow will mainly be dealing with derived data. Other file formats can be used while processing/analysing the data, but it is encouraged to convert to a recommended file format before archiving/publishing the data. Ideally, file formats should be non-proprietary (open), unencrypted, uncompressed, and commonly used by the research community. If it's not possible to use one of these file formats, the software name, version, license, and company should be documented in the metadata.

Table 1 – Overview of file formats.

Data type	Data format
Genetic data – raw: sequences	FASTQ / FASTA / FAS
Genetic data - derived	CSV / TSV
Plankton imaging data – raw: images	TIFF / PNG/ JPG
Plankton imaging data - derived	CSV / TSV
Biologging data – raw	TBRARW / VRL / CSV
Biologging data - derived	CSV / TSV
Passive acoustic data – raw	WAV
Passive acoustic data – derived	CSV / TSV
Other sources	CSV / TSV / ... (to be determined)

2.3. Data re-use

Data sources will include data owners of missing data identified in WP2 Task 2.2, data providers engaged through the two FSTP calls organised in WP2 Task 2.5, existing networks and monitoring programs generating steady and continuous biodiversity data addressed through WP3, other EU funded projects, and integrators and repositories of biodiversity data. Data owners of missing data identified in T2.2 will be encouraged to apply to the second FSTP call organised in T2.5. An overview of the selected grant holders of the first call of Task 2.5 can be found in *Annex 1*. For an overview of integrators, repositories and EU funded projects identified as possible data sources, see the **D3.1 DTO-BioFlow data flow Blueprint** document. The aim of the project is to establish data flows from these different sources to EMODnet Biology and to the EU DTO.

2.4. Data size

Data size is difficult to assess and will become clearer as the project progresses. In cases of genetic, acoustic and bioglogging data, size might range into multiple GBs per dataset.

2.5. Data utility

By unlocking and sustaining biodiversity data flows to a functioning and integrated biodiversity component of the DTO, DTO-BioFlow will deliver a step change in EU capacity to monitor, measure, manage, protect and restore our marine and coastal ecosystems. Supporting the Mission lighthouses and Blue Parks platform, DTO-BioFlow outcomes will facilitate achievement of the Mission objectives, the ambitions of the European Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 targets, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. New evidence-based knowledge on marine biodiversity and how it is impacted by multiple human activities and environmental pressures (including climate change) will support the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (and its review), the Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) Directive and the Common Fisheries Policy. DTO-BioFlow activities will mobilise a committed and DTO-aware marine biodiversity monitoring and user community, which extends beyond the scientific community to include data collectors/providers from industry, public bodies and citizen organisations. Data, innovative concepts, methodologies and new evidence-based knowledge, deriving from multidisciplinary and cross-domain research, will be shared with the DTO development community building digital twinning capacity, advancing the delivery of a fit-for-purpose EU DTO and contributing to the success of the UN Decade of Ocean Science.

3. Data flow

DTO-BioFlow aims to establish data flows from different sources (more information see section 2.3.) to the EU DTO. *In situ* marine biodiversity data will flow via EMODnet Biology to the EU DTO. EMODnet Biology has at its core a data infrastructure which is shared with EuroBIS – the European OBIS node. All data made available in EMODnet Biology can flow to OBIS and GBIF via the EuroBIS IPT instance. For biological data that does not fit in EMODnet Biology, a direct connection to the DTO will be explored and if possible, implemented. For a schematic overview of the data flow towards EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO, see *Figure 1*.

GENERAL

Figure 1 – Envisaged general data flow diagram towards EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO.

For a more detailed description of the envisioned data flow, see the **D3.1 DTO-BioFlow data flow Blueprint** document. The Blueprint also contains more specific details on the envisioned data flow for each of the targeted subcategories of biological data (i.e. genomics observation networks; plankton imaging observation networks; fish, mammal and bird biollogging networks; cetacean passive acoustic observation networks; and other relevant biodiversity data sources). For some sources, data flows are currently lacking, and for other sources data flows to EMODnet Biology are already in place but will be improved within the scope of the project.

4. FAIR data

FAIR refers to the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reuse of digital datasets¹.

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data **findability** will be assured by the assignment of a globally unique and persistent identifier, in addition to the publication of a metadata record. VLIZ will offer the possibility of assigning a persistent identifier through its DOI-service in the VLIZ Data Centre. Metadata and keywords will be added in line with the requirements for the EMODnet Biology repository and EDITO-INFRA data lake, as well as other relevant repositories which are of use in the range of data flows set up in this project. EMODnet Biology and the EDITO-INFRA data lake both allow harvesting of metadata.

4.2. Making data openly accessible

All data and other research outputs will be made openly **available** by deposition in trusted repositories. The data flows established in this project will inject the data and data products in the EMODnet Biology data repository and the EDITO-Infra data lake, ensuring they become FAIR and Openly Accessible and preserved after the project's end. Data will preferably be stored in non-proprietary file formats which can be handled by open software (file formats depending on data type, see 2.2.2.). Metadata will be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0 and will contain information to enable the user to access the data.

4.3. Making data interoperable

Data will adhere to standard formats and be as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, facilitating **interoperability**.

Several of the envisioned repositories already use vocabularies, standards and formats, which include:

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

- DarwinCore standard for biodiversity data;
- BODC NERC Vocabularies: controlled vocabularies, for example for parameter names;
- Marine Regions: a standard list of marine georeferenced place names and areas;
- World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS): an authoritative classification and catalogue of marine taxon names;
- MIxS: a metadata standard for sequence data.

In case new ontologies or vocabularies need to be developed, they will be openly published.

Within WP5 (Integration in DTO infrastructure), Task 5.2 will work on interoperability, compatibility & aligning with DTO & other initiatives. This task will ensure the data streams are based on Digital-Twin-ready standards as developed by other ongoing initiatives (e.g., EDITO-Infra, Iliad, BioDT, DITTO, TURTLE, EOSC) and become part of the EMODnet infrastructure. Aligning with these projects will ensure consolidated standards, protocols between different infrastructures and interoperability in terms of workflows where models or digital twin applications can be run on multiple infrastructures, based on similar tools & services. Requirements and design principles will be transferred between projects to harmonise the tools & services from different projects. An aligned set of requirements, design principles, service interfaces and data standards for cross-project collaboration will be described in D5.1 (Interoperability report).

4.4. Increase data re-use

The data flows established in this project will inject the data and data products in the EMODnet Biology data repositories and the EDITO-Infra data lake, ensuring they become FAIR and Openly Accessible and preserved after the project's end. The data and other research outputs will be **useable** by third parties. The provenance and license of the data and other research outputs will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards. All data streams will be matched to the quality criteria of EMODnet Biology, or those of other repositories where necessary.

5. Other research outputs

Data products resulting from this project will mostly be made available via EMODnet Biology. Other relevant outputs will be fed into Zenodo, a multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN (<https://zenodo.org/>), while selected scientific publications and technical results will also be presented and submitted to relevant journals of impact factor of at least 3.0.

6. Allocation of resources

A budget of €1,000,000 is included in the project to support data holders of marine biodiversity (monitoring) data outside of the consortium to establish data flows to the DTO through FSTP grants of maximum €60,000. All other activities for setting up and executing the data streams are covered within the rest of the project's budget. There are no costs for the use of the data systems envisioned in this project.

Flanders Marine Institute will oversee the data management of the project and act as the data controller, while all consortium partners are data processors.

7. Data security

The project will strive for automated and self-sustaining data flows. Data streams will be built using existing and trusted data repositories, making use of their data security initiatives. Hence the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation.

8. Ethical aspects

DTO-BioFlow work focuses mainly on data generation and data management, on the development of standards and protocols to optimise the harmonisation of biodiversity-relevant data collection which may be ongoing by DTO-BioFlow partners and other initiatives. In doing so, it abides by the key principle of EMODnet “to collect data once and use it many times”. By making data FAIR, available to primary & secondary data aggregators, and ultimately to wider society through the EU DTO, DTO-BioFlow enables the re-use of data thus reducing the need for repeated unnecessary data collection and any associated environmental impact thereof.

There may be some new data collection as part of the test-casing activities in WP3, but these would be carried out according to best-practice as regards animal welfare and environmental considerations. Project partners will adhere to the ‘do no significant harm’ principle as per Article 17 of Regulation (EU) No 2020/852 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment (i.e. the so-called 'EU Taxonomy Regulation'). Any and all invasive procedures (e.g., tagging of species with acoustic transmitters) will be undertaken within EU and respective national regulations and guidelines with project and personal licences obtained in advance of any fieldwork taking place. The deployment of any scientific research equipment will be subject to relevant national and EU regulations with the necessary licences and permissions obtained in advance.

Personal information concerning all project participants, end-users of the various use cases and applications/demonstrators, members of External Advisory Board (EAB) and citizen scientists and other community members engaged via events, outreach initiatives, the DTO-Bioflow portal, and via social media, will be kept confidential under the privacy statement and terms & conditions outlined on the website www.dto-bioflow.eu (VLIZ: Data controller; consortium partners: Data processors), and in line with the DTO-BioFlow Strategy for addressing the ethics (see D1.5).

9. Other issues

Data management activities will be coordinated by the VLIZ data centre, which is an internationally accredited data centre due to their standardized procedures. In any case, VLIZ will aim to adhere to the FAIR principles, the data policies of the used repositories and systems, as well as the statements within this DMP. Project partners will be urged to implement internal procedures to streamline data management activities. In cases where partners lack the necessary procedures, VLIZ will aid in the creation of one.

10. Annexes

10.1. Annex 1 – Overview of selected grant holders

Table 2 – Overview of selected grant holders from the first open data call.

Project title	Organisation	Data description
Integration of southeastern Mediterranean long-term biodiversity data into EU-DTO	Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research, government research institute	Southeastern Mediterranean biodiversity data, collated in the ISRAMARBIO database
KAIROS - Zooplankton data from Arctic marine time-series to understand biodiversity dynamics	National Research Council, Institute of Polar Sciences (CNR-ISP) + National Research Council, Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems (CNRIRET)	Zooplankton biodiversity data from sediment traps in Svalbard collected in the framework of the Italian Arctic Marine Observing System
Managing and publishing biodiversity data from Nord University	Faculty of Biosciences and Aquaculture, Nord University	Biodiversity data from Nord University, such as data from zooplankton trawls, benthos grabs and undersea videos
Management and publication of Marine Characterisation Research Project data	Menter Môn, UK	Biodiversity data collected in the framework of the Marine Characterisation Research Project collected through a variety of methods, such as passive acoustic monitoring, sonar cameras, RGB and infrared cameras, acoustic deterrent devices (ADDs), drone and boat-based observations, seal and seabird tagging and shore-based population counts.
Marine Megafauna Data for EU Digital Twin Ocean	Bangor University, School of Ocean Sciences & School of Computer Science and Engineering + Sea Watch Foundation	Marine megafauna sightings in European seas collected by the UK Sea Watch Foundation (SWF) and its partners.
Strandaanspoel (beach washup) Monitoring Project (SMP)	Stichting ANEMOON (Netherlands), foundation, NGO	Biodiversity data collected along the Dutch shoreline in the framework of the Strandaanspoel Monitoring Project (SMP)
Plankton Imaging Data Flow: Establishing a European data flow for phyto- and microzooplankton data from automated AI-assisted imaging in flow analyses	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute	Phyto- and microzooplankton data from Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) in European waters
Futurismo: linking whale watching tourism with cetacean research in the Azores.	Futurismo Azores Adventures	Cetacean sightings by Futurismo (whale-watching tourism) in the Azores
Pipeline for biodiversity data from the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) to the OBIS network and EMODnet.	National Oceanography Centre	Biodiversity data of the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC)

10.2. Annex 2 – Template of agreement with selected grant holders

DTO-BioFlow Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) grant agreement

Participation in the “Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data” to set up a sustained flow of biodiversity data to the Digital Twin of the Ocean

The following Agreement is hereby concluded by and between:

The **Flanders Marine Institute NPO, 8400 Ostend, Jacobsenstraat 1, Belgium**, with company number **0466.279.196** represented by the General Director, Jan Mees (VLIZ),

AND

The **[Organisation name]**, having its registered office at **[Adress]**, with company number **[Company number]** represented by its [function] [name] (hereby referred to as the recipient).

WHEREAS VLIZ is coordinator of “Project 101112523 – DTO BioFlow”. To deliver on its responsibilities within this contract and linked to Work Package 2, Task 2.5 : organise open calls to data holders.

BOTH PARTIES HAVE AGREED TO THE FOLLOWING

Art. 1: FSTP grant specifications:

This grant is issued in the framework of the “DTO-BioFlow project”. DTO-BioFlow will develop and integrate the biological component of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), including new digital tools and services, by combining sustained data flows, models, and new algorithms.

This grant contributes to Work Package 2 (WP2): Increasing the flow of relevant biodiversity data. The aim of the grant is to support the recipient in setting up a sustained flow of biodiversity data to the Digital Twin of the Ocean.

Art. 2: Expected outcomes and deliverables.

Description of the data for which a sustained data flow is being established:	[Data description]
Description of the dataset(s) that will become available to EMODnet Biology at the end of the project:	[Dataset description]

The recipient is committed to carry out the following activities:

- 2.1 Participate in the data training workshop held **22-24 April 2024** in Ostend (Belgium). At least one person should attend the workshop in person.
- 3.1 Ensure all data is formatted, standardized, and quality controlled in conformance with the relevant international standards (as demonstrated in the workshop).
- 4.1 Ensure the data complies with Open Access, preferably under a Creative Commons CC-BY license.
- 5.1 Ensure that the current data (description see table above) and its metadata are ready for harvesting by EMODnet Biology by the end of the project (February 28, 2025).
- 6.1 Submit short intermediary progress reports every four months (by June 30th, 2024, and October 31st, 2024). The results report is to be submitted at the end of the project.
- 7.1 Commit to continue to publish new data (description see table above) regularly, also after the end of the contract (by updating datasets created during the project with new records or by publishing new datasets), and thus contributing to the sustained flow of marine biodiversity data into EMODnet Biology and the DTO, ideally facilitated by (semi-)automated data flow pipelines.
- 8.1 Deliver any other relevant outcomes which were described in the proposal [FSTP project title]

Art. 3: Duration and deadlines

- 3.1 This FSTP Grant Agreement will start as from **March 1, 2024** and has a term of 12 months.
- 4.1 As mentioned in Art. 2, all deliverables are to be submitted within the expected deadlines (see overview table below).

Deliverable	Deadline
Intermediary progress report 1	Jun 30, 2024
Intermediary progress report 2	Oct 31, 2024
Final Results Report	Feb 28, 2025
Data ready for EMODnet Biology	Feb 28, 2025

Art. 4: Financing

The total amount of the FSTP grant agreed for the work defined is **[budget] Euros** ([budget written in full]).

The received funding can be used exclusively for the following costs and only for the project [FSTP project title]

- 1. Personnel costs to execute the following types of activities:**
 - o Data collation, data processing, reformatting, standardization, transfer, and publication.
 - o Development of (semi-)automated pipelines for the above activities.
 - o Development of data access API's (Application Programming Interface).
 - o Data quality control.
 - o Data documentation and management (in accordance with FAIR principles).
- 2. Travel costs to attend the data training workshop (22-24 April 2024, Ostend).**

The payment shall be made on the basis of **two invoices with specification of POnumber [PO number]** to be sent to **“Invoice VLIZ and Leen Vandepitte”** (invoice@vliz.be; leen.vandepitte@vliz.be).

The second payment will be subject to the acceptance of the deliverables and outcomes as indicated in Article 2 of this contract.

All payments shall be made within 30 days of the date of the invoice.

The payment scheme will be as follows:

1. First payment of 50% or **[50% of budget] Euros** ([50% of budget written in full]), at the start of the project and after signing of the FSTP Grant Agreement.
2. Final payment of 50% or **[50% of budget]** ([50% of budget written in full]) will be made after the acceptance of the submitted data, deliverables and outcomes and upon final completion of 28/02/2025.

The payments shall be made to:

Organisation name	[Organisation name]
Address	[Address]
SWIFT/BIC	[SWIFT/BIC]
Account number (IBAN)	[Account number (IBAN)]

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For [Organisation name]:
(Date & signature)

For VLIZ :

[Name],
[Function]

Jan Mees
General Director